

On Generating an Integrated DSS from a Mathematical Model Specification *

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Abstract

Executable mathematical modeling languages (EMLs), designed to facilitate model representation and execution, are traditionally weak in data modeling and management, which often constitutes a majority of the effort in a modeling project. In this paper, we describe a systematic approach for developing an integrated decision support system given an EML model. This approach is first demonstrated using a model for flight scheduling, integrating a formal data model, represented in a database management system, and a mathematical model, represented in an EML (GAMS). Next, we present a generalized procedure that, for any mathematical model represented in GAMS, produces a data model and a primitive user interface for the mathematical model. Benefits of this approach include explicit data modeling, improved representation and manipulation of model inputs and outputs, greater integrity of input data, and easier interpretation and multiple views of model outputs.

1 Introduction

Decision support systems (DSS) aim to facilitate the use of data and models in decision making [1]. These systems typically have three components, namely for dialog, data, and model management. While the critical and distinctive feature of a DSS is the use of mathematical or other models in the decision making process, few DSS generators (software for develop-

ing DSS) have sufficient features for model representation, execution, and management. Builders of model-based DSS, therefore, usually employ a *model-oriented* approach such as executable algebraic modeling languages [2] or other kinds of interfaces to mathematical solvers, even though these tend to be weak on data and dialog management. One representative and popular language in this category is the model representation language in GAMS (General Algebraic Modeling System [3]). GAMS provides an algebraic language for representing mathematical models, as well as automatic translators to a number of solvers for optimization models.

In model-oriented languages such as GAMS,¹ the “model file” actually consists of a rudimentary “data definition” (or data model) and control statements for presentation of the output, in addition to a declaration of the mathematical equations. Few guidelines or design principles—well known and accepted in the database management literature—for *data* definition are enforced in such languages (SML [4, 5], based on structured modeling [6], is a notable exception to this claim) [7]. The lack of a formal data model, and of a management system for the data schema and the data base, leads to several problems, including those concerned with model maintenance, data integrity, alternative views of the input data, management of multiple input and output data sets, and meaningful presen-

¹We single out GAMS in this paper not because we intend to criticize it (in fact the authors believe GAMS is a great contribution to mathematical modeling), but because our motivating problem happened to be a GAMS model. Since GAMS is a good representative of the algebraic approach to modeling, our results easily generalize to other algebraic languages and systems.

*File: downs-dss-hicss96.tex. Please address correspondence to Hemant Bhargava.

tation of solutions. Further, since data management comprises a majority of effort in the use of a model, the lack of data management features is certainly a limiting factor in modeling languages.

Using a flight scheduling problem, this paper illustrates (in §2) how to integrate a mathematical model—originally implemented in a model-oriented language (specifically, GAMS)—with a formal and explicit data model for the problem domain. The result is a complete, integrated DSS: the data model is implemented in a database management system (Paradox); model representation and modification continues to be performed in GAMS. The database system is also used to provide a superior (to the GAMS interface) *general* user interface as well as a *customized* user interface for working with data; however we do not discuss the user interface in this paper. The interface is used to control model instantiation and execution, including the setting up of input files for the mathematical solver, and the extraction of the solution from the solver's report. For generality, we use pseudocode based on SQL (Structured Query Language [8]) syntax to describe queries required to create the database and retrieve data. Next, in §3, we demonstrate how this approach alleviates the problems referred to above.

Of course, developing the integrated DSS requires a significant amount of programming which would not be particularly useful if it were not generalizable. Section 4 of this paper presents a systematic, generalized version of the solution mentioned above. It develops a method for automatically generating the database schemas, queries, and interface programs that comprise the integrated system. Importantly, this method requires from the modeler only a table summarizing the data definition portion of the "model" declaration.

2 An Integrated DSS for Flight Scheduling

In this section, we discuss how a complete integrated DSS is created for a GAMS-based model—the USMC Trainee model—for the scheduling of training flights in a U.S. Marine Corps squadron. An integer programming model for determining optimal flight schedules is described in [9]. The data definition portion of this model—*sans* the detailed data—is given in Appendix A.

The flight schedule document coordinates all activity in a squadron on a daily basis. It lists missions to be conducted, the pilots assigned to fly the missions, and aircraft to be used. The inputs to the flight scheduling process are the training events to be ac-

complished, students available to fly, instructors available to teach, and flight hours available for a given day. The output of the flight schedule process—the schedule—lists every event that the squadron will fly on the following day. Every event has an event number, launch time, recovery time, aircrew, aircraft to be flown, and other notes concerning the flight. The schedule represents the scheduler's best estimated use of the squadron's pilots, flight hours and aircraft.

2.1 Structure of the Model File

The need to separate model from detailed data is well-accepted and encouraged in modeling languages [10]. This principle is only weakly enforced in GAMS. That is, even though the model and data are defined separately, detailed data is often included in the model file, and is required before any operations can be performed on the model. However, GAMS does provide an option to separate the detailed data from the model file. This is done, for each input term (set, parameter, table and scalar), by replacing detailed data with an **\$include** statement, which specifies the file from which detailed data may be read. Our method assumes that the model file has been set up in this manner; Figure 1 shows a sample GAMS file with detailed data and one with a call to a separate data file. One objective of our integrated system is to generate these data files using database queries. The method also applies to other modeling languages such as AMPL [11] that separate model and data more explicitly.

2.2 Design of the Data Model

Data modeling involves determining and representing 1) the objects about which data must be maintained, 2) the characteristics of these objects that are of interest to the users, and 3) the relationships between the objects [12]. When designing a database to support a mathematical model, the objects, characteristics and relationships of the objects can be taken directly from the mathematical model. On the other hand, if an independent database already existed, then one would simply develop a mapping between elements of the database and elements of the mathematical model. Here, we construct a data model assuming that no such database exists. Given the data definition segment of a GAMS model, it is fairly straightforward to develop a 3rd normal form database design for the model. This process is illustrated below on fragments of the data definition. For ease of automation, when developing the database schema, we use the same names for database relations as were used in the GAMS model.

<pre> PARAMETER HBAR(Q) max flt hrs / Gulman 3, Weigl 0 Grace 4, Emery 1 ... / </pre>	<pre> PARAMETER HBAR(Q) max flt hrs / #include "c:\flight\hbar.txt" / </pre>
---	--

Figure 1: Using the **\$include** statement to separate detailed data. The statements in the left box represent a GAMS file that contains detailed data for parameter HBAR(Q). The statements in the right box refer to a separate file for data.

Unless it is clear from the context, we use the following notation to distinguish between GAMS components, database relations, and database attributes: GAMS names are written in bold face (e.g., **Q**), database names are italicized; further, database relations are underscored (e.g., Q is a relation, while *Q* is an attribute in the relation Q).

The complete Trainee database schema is given in Appendix B; it would be useful to compare this with the GAMS data definition given in Appendix A. General rules for determining the database design are stated in §4.2; Procedure 1 implements these rules using SQL-like syntax to create the database schema.

1. The set **Q** of instructors in the GAMS model is represented via a database relation Q. This relation has an attribute *Q* as its key, and other attributes depending on model parameters that are indexed on **Q** (see below). Similarly, the set **I** of events is represented via a relation I. The alias **J** (of **I**) is represented as a virtual relation J—a copy of relation I.
2. The parameter **HBAR(Q)** is represented as an attribute *HBAR* of the relation Q. Other parameters indexed on **Q**, if any, would also become attributes in Q.
3. The table **Qual(I,Q)** is represented as a relation Qual, whose (composite) key is (*I,Q*), and which has an attribute *Qual*. *I* and *Q* are foreign keys in Qual. Similarly, any GAMS table becomes a database relation having the table's index sets as its foreign keys and an attribute that describes the GAMS table data.

In our design, each GAMS table or indexed variable results in a new relation, even if some other tables were indexed on the same sets. The alternative is to create a single relation for variables indexed on the same sets. However, such a relation would be inflexible in handling data sparsity in certain cases, since it would only be

able to eliminate those rows in which all non-key attributes have zero or (default) values. While our design choice results in more database relations, it offers more flexibility in handling the problem of data sparsity in the relations created. A default value can now be attached with each relation, and only non-default values need to be specified explicitly.

4. Scalar inputs are single values, and may be associated with a database relation, or can be obtained from the user directly at the time of program execution. We assume the latter approach in this paper.

2.3 Links from the Database to the Modelbase

Once a database schema for the model has been designed and instantiated, one must construct linkages between the two. Here, we describe the linkages required to export instantiating data to the mathematical modeling system.

1. **Determine the input required for the model.**

The inputs for a GAMS mathematical model are sets, parameters, tables and scalars. Examples of input requirements for each of these object types are summarized in Table 1. Generalized rules for determining the input requirements are stated in §4.3.1.

2. **Determine required database queries.**

Table 2 illustrates, using our example objects, the SQL queries required to extract input data for the GAMS model. Procedure 2, presented in §4.3.2, automatically generates these queries.

3. **Generate input data files for mathematical model.**

Object Type	Object	FROM	SELECT
Set	Q	<u>Q</u>	Q
Parameter	HBAR(Q)	<u>Q</u>	Q, HBAR
Table	Qual(I,Q)	<u>Qual</u>	I, Q, Qual

Table 1: Fields required from database relation for objects Q, HBAR(Q), and Qual(I,Q).

GAMS		Database		
Input	Type	Key	Attribute	Relation
Q	Set	Q		<u>Q</u>
HBAR(Q)	Parameter	Q	HBAR	<u>Q</u>
Qual(Q)	Table	I,Q	Qual	<u>Qual</u>

Query for Set Q:
SELECT Q FROM Q

Query for Parameter HBAR(Q):
SELECT Q, HBAR FROM Q

Query for Table Qual(I,Q):
SELECT I, Q, Qual FROM Qual

Table 2: Sample model/data elements, and Queries.

The results of the database queries are stored as database relations. To export this data to the mathematical model, each relation must be suitably converted (see Figure 2) and placed in an appropriate location for GAMS to access. An interface program (see Figure 3) performs these steps as follows: 1) an SQL query creates a virtual relation (a *view*) by retrieving relevant data from the database, 2) an ObjectPal—a Paradox Application Language—procedure (exportASCIIvar) converts the view into an ASCII file, with suitable punctuations, and stores the file in the corresponding location mentioned in the \$include statement in the model file. This is done for each set, parameter, or table in the GAMS model. A generalized procedure for producing such interface programs (Procedure 3) is described in §4.3.3.

2.4 Links from the Modelbase to the Database

Once the GAMS model is instantiated and solved, relevant parts of the results must be read back into the database. This could be done either via an interpreter program that reads the .LST file produced by GAMS,

Figure 2: Conversion of database query result to GAMS format

```

SELECT Q, HBAR                                (1)
FROM Q

exportASCIIvar("HBAR", "HBAR.TXT",          (2)
"HBAREXP", TRUE)
    
```

Figure 3: Paradox interface program for exporting input data to GAMS data files. The file "HBAR.TXT" is read into GAMS via an \$include statement.

or by adding some control statements in the GAMS model file; we choose the latter approach. The procedure is described, using a GAMS solution table as an example, in the following 4 steps. Such a procedure would be written for each solution table that needs to be imported into Paradox.

1. Identify the mathematical model output that is desired to be exported to the database (e.g., the $\mathbf{X(I,P)}$ which is set to 1 if student P performs item I).
2. Modify the mathematical model to export the results to an output file, as explained in the following steps and illustrated in Figure 4.
 - (a) Create an alias file in GAMS to store results (in the figure, `training.txt` is the alias file for $\mathbf{X(I,P)}$)
 - (b) Direct GAMS to send outputs to this file
 - (c) Direct GAMS to write output in a text-quoted, comma-delimited format
 - (d) Restructure GAMS output (key fields along vertical and horizontal axes, values in the body) into a Paradox-interpretable format (key1, key2, attribute)
3. Design a database relation to accept the mathematical model data.
4. Read in the solution table into the database:

```
importASCIIvar("training.txt", "training",
              ", " , " " , True, True)
```

3 Integrated DSS or GAMS model: A Comparison

We argue that this integrated DSS for flight scheduling offers significant advantages over a pure GAMS implementation of the flight scheduling model and data. We do so by comparing the process of scheduling training flights under the two approaches. First, consider a typical sequence of tasks that one must perform to generate daily flight schedules.

1. Determine what set of instructors and students are available for inclusion into the day's flight schedule.
2. Enter or edit the model's sets. Instructors and students who are added to or deleted from the sets must also be added to or deleted from each parameter and table where they are represented.

3. Enter or edit parameters and tables. An example of a recurring update requirement is the parameter DHAT(P) which represents the number of days that a pilot P has been assigned for training. Each day the scheduler must increment the number of days that each student has been available for training.
4. Run the GAMS model.
5. Read and interpret the GAMS output.

While a pure GAMS implementation allows model instances to be created and solved, the process has drawbacks in several aspects of the complete modeling process, as argued in §1. We discuss specific areas of weakness in this section. The point of the discussion is not simply that certain operations are hard to perform; rather it is that these weaknesses materially affect the quality of the modeling process and solution, e.g., by limiting the number of scenarios that a modeler can examine.

3.1 Input and Modification of Instantiating Data: Interface Issues

In the GAMS data model a "table," or relation, is created for each *set*, *parameter* and *table*. Since several tables and parameters may be defined over the same index sets, data about the same objects (i.e., elements of the index sets) is fragmented across several tables. This approach increases chances of errors. For example, to create data for a new index set, first elements of the set are declared. Following that, tables must be created for the parameters and tables indexed on that set; these tables must mention the set elements again, resulting in a high risk of inconsistent spellings. Debugging of syntactic errors such as misspellings and misplaced punctuations consumes enormous time and causes a lot of frustration. These problems are entirely avoided in our "integrated" approach, since the final GAMS data representation is generated from the database, and since a particular element is entered only once in the database.

Similarly, if an element is added in GAMS to a set, corresponding additions must be made to the associated parameters and tables, and these insertions must be made along the correct rows and columns. This process is cumbersome, time consuming and error-prone. It provides no structural support, relying on the user's physical skills, e.g., to ensure that insertions are made at appropriate places or that tables are complete (each row has as many elements as the table preamble requires). Again, a database simplifies this process tremendously.

FILE TRN /'C:\training.txt' /	(a)
PUT TRN;	(b)
TRN.PC = 5;	(c)
LOOP(IP(I,P)\$X.L(I,P)) PUT P.TL, I.TL /);	(d)

Figure 4: GAMS interface program for exporting solution data to Paradox data files.

3.2 Input and Modification of Instantiating Data: Logical Issues

The lack of a formal model for the GAMS data means that certain relationships are lost. E.g., consider the relation between an index set P and an indexed variable $DHAT(P)$. If captured formally, it would ensure that instances of $DHAT(P)$ could be created only for elements of P (making it impossible to enter a value for, say, $DHAT(\text{James})$ if James is not already in P), or that if an instance of P were deleted, corresponding elements would be deleted from $DHAT(P)$ as well as all other variables indexed on P . All of these checks are eventually done in GAMS, but only when the entire model file is compiled.

Formal constructs from data modeling—such as the concepts of *keys*, *foreign keys*, and *functional dependencies*—can be used to impose integrity constraints on, say, input data for a model [7]. The database management system automatically ensures that these constraints are satisfied by instance data. This is done either via the system's interface for data entry—data that do not satisfy the constraints are not accepted—or by performing integrity checks on the database.

3.3 Working with Multiple Model Instances

The model and data manipulation features in GAMS, as well as in other modeling systems, are designed for working with a single instance at a time, and do not support managing, analyzing or comparing multiple model instances. Multiple solution sets cannot be stored without saving a copy of the integrated GAMS data and model. In the flight scheduling context, this results in little support for analyzing and comparing multiple problem scenarios during a single day, or for doing the same across time, or for building an archive of schedules. This is often called the *scenario management* problem [13]. Many of the issues in scenario management, for which there is little support in GAMS, can be addressed via standard database management features.

3.4 Interpretation of Solutions

Solution sets produced in GAMS are hard to read and interpret, chiefly because the results are presented in a single format, making it hard for users to focus on particular aspects of the solution, or to view a solution from different perspectives.

Under our DSS approach, the GAMS output is presented to the user through a database management system. Again, database systems provide standard features for creating multiple views from complex data sets (see §3.5). Output screens and reports can be customized within the DSS to highlight the data that is most important to different users, and this data can be displayed in different ways such as tables and graphs.

3.5 Manipulation of Input and Output Data

The methods for storing and representing both input and output data in GAMS offer no support for standard manipulation functions such as sorting, selecting (via restrictions on rows, columns, or attributes), and mathematical aggregation. Even a simple operation such as sorting is sometimes quite valuable in understanding, or getting insight from, a large data set. The lack of such operations restricts users to a single view of the data, making it hard to do any analysis with the data. In the DSS, using standard database query and manipulation operations and graphical representations, many different views can be generated for both input and output data.

4 A Generalized Approach for Integrating the Data and Mathematical Models

Now we discuss how to automate the process, explained in §2, of developing an integrated DSS for a mathematical model. First, we discuss the metadata that this automation process requires (§4.1), then we present procedures—parameterized on this metadata—

for automating a) the database design (§4.2), b) the linkages from the database to the modelbase (§4.3), and c) the reverse linkages for the model solution (§4.4).

4.1 Metadata for Generalization Program

Our strategy in automating the development of an integrated DSS is to parameterize the tasks one must perform to develop the database schemas, queries, and interface programs. For a specific mathematical model, the tasks' parameters are obtained from the data definition portion of the model—these parameter values are what we called the metadata required to develop the integrated DSS. With the parameterized representation of the tasks, the integration procedures can automatically be performed given the model-specific metadata. Table 3 illustrates the structure of this metadata by presenting a fragment of the metadata required to integrate the USMC trainee model. Such a table might be constructed by the modeler, or it may automatically be generated by interpreting the model's data definition statements.

4.2 Database Design

The relations, and characteristics or attributes of the relations, required to design a database for a mathematical model are found by examining the sets, parameters, and tables of the model. General rules for determining the relations are given below.

Design Rule 1 *Each set of singletons in the mathematical model is represented as a relation in the data model. The relation will have, as key, a field corresponding to the index name.*

Design Rule 2 *Each set of n -tuples in the mathematical model is represented in the data model as a relation, whose key is composed of names corresponding to the n elements in the tuple.*

Design Rule 3 *An alias set S' of set S is represented as a virtual relation S' which is a copy of relation S .*

Design Rule 4 *Singly-indexed parameters in the mathematical model are represented in the data model as fields (or attributes) of the relation corresponding to the index set.*

Consider parameters $IBAR(P)$, $DHAT(P)$, and $NC(P)$. The database relation \underline{P} has four fields: one key field P , and three attributes $IBAR$, $DHAT$ and NC .

Design Rule 5 *Tables in the mathematical model, indexed on multiple index sets, are represented as an attribute of a new relation whose key consists of the corresponding index names (these are also designated as foreign keys).*

Consider table $Qual(I,Q)$. The relation $Qual$ has a composite key consisting of the item name I and instructor name Q , corresponding to sets I and Q . It also has an attribute $Qual$ —the instructor's qualification to teach the event. The designation of I and Q as foreign keys (referring to I and Q respectively) ensures referential integrity for $Qual(I,Q)$. This idea generalizes to "tables" that are indexed on more than 2 sets as well.

A generalized procedure that applies these rules to construct the database schema using information from Table 3 is given below. In the first part of Step 1, relations are constructed for sets in the mathematical model; in Step 2, attributes are added to these relations for the parameters in the model. In the second part of Step 1, relations are created for tables in the model.

Procedure 1 Database Design

- Step 1

```

OPEN TABLE META_DATA
WHILE NOT END_OF_TABLE
  READ RECORD
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "SET" THEN
    CREATE TABLE <GAMS-NAME>
    ( <GAMS-NAME>, CHAR(10),
      PRIMARY KEY <GAMS-NAME> )
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "TABLE" THEN
    CREATE TABLE <GAMS-NAME>
    ( <INDEX1>, CHAR(10),
      <INDEX2>, CHAR(10),
      PRIMARY KEY (<INDEX1>,<INDEX2>),
      <GAMS-NAME>, FLOAT,
      FOREIGN KEY <INDEX1>,
      FOREIGN KEY <INDEX2> )
  ENDWHILE
CLOSE TABLE META_DATA
    
```

- Step 2

```

OPEN TABLE META_DATA
WHILE NOT END_OF_TABLE
  READ RECORD
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "PARAMETER" THEN
    ALTER TABLE <INDEX1> ADD
    <GAMS-NAME> FLOAT
  ENDWHILE
CLOSE TABLE META_DATA
    
```

GAMS-TYPE	GAMS-NAME	INDEX1	INDEX2	DB-NAME	FILE-NAME
SET	P			P	P.txt
SET	I			I	I.txt
PARAMETER	IBAR	P		IBAR	IBAR.txt
TABLE	PROG	I	P	PROG	PROG.txt

Table 3: Fragment of metadata required for generalized procedures

4.3 Linkages from Database to Modelbase

Now we describe generalized procedures which can be executed to create the linkages from the database to the modeling system. We follow the sequence of steps illustrated in §2.3.

4.3.1 Determine the input required for the model

The inputs for a GAMS mathematical model are sets, parameters, tables and scalars. The input requirements for each of these are summarized in the following rules.

1. Each mathematical model set requires the key fields from its corresponding database relation.
2. Each mathematical model parameter requires the key field and an attribute from its corresponding database relation.
3. Each mathematical table requires the (two or more) foreign keys and the single attribute from its corresponding database association relation.

4.3.2 Determine required database queries

The queries required to retrieve input data for the model can be specified via rules based on whether the input object is a set, parameter, or table. Procedure 2 implements these rules.

Procedure 2 Query Generation

```

OPEN TABLE META_DATA
WHILE NOT END_OF_TABLE
READ RECORD
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "SET" THEN
    SELECT <GAMS-NAME>
    FROM <DB-NAME> SAVE AS <GAMS-NAME>
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "PARAMETER" THEN
    SELECT <INDEX1>, <GAMS-NAME>
    FROM <INDEX1> SAVE AS <GAMS-NAME>
  IF <GAMS-TYPE> = "TABLE" THEN

```

```

SELECT <INDEX1>, <INDEX2>, <GAMS-NAME>
FROM <DB-NAME> SAVE AS <GAMS-NAME>
ENDWHILE
CLOSE TABLE META_DATA

```

4.3.3 Conversion of database relations to mathematical model inputs

As described in §3, interface programs are required to reformat and export the results of database queries into GAMS-readable files. A generalized procedure that produces—again using the information in Table 3—these programs is described below. Step 1 involves a modification of the GAMS file to replace detailed data with a call to the data file. Step 2 generates a script for each object to export data from Paradox to the appropriate data file.

Procedure 3 Exporting Data into GAMS

- Step 1: Mathematical model modification.
For each object in the meta-data table, replace the mathematical model input data with:

```

"$include "operating system path\  
<meta-data-table.FILE-NAME>.TXT"

```

- Step 2: Database modification (Paradox specific).

```

CREATE EXPORT SCRIPT
OPEN TABLE META_DATA
WHILE NOT END_OF_TABLE
  READ RECORD
  WRITE "EXPORTASCIIVAR("<GAMS-NAME>","
    "<GAMS-NAME>.TXT",
    "<QUERY-RESULT-STRUCT>"," TRUE);
ENDWHILE
CLOSE TABLE

```

4.4 Linkages from Modelbase to Database

The results of the mathematical model, controlled in GAMS via the DISPLAY statement, must be exported

into the database relations. We describe informally in procedure 4 a method for modifying the GAMS file to export the outputs to a file, and for importing this file into the database.

Procedure 4 *Exporting Solutions from GAMS to Database*

- Step 1: Directing GAMS solution data into a structured text file.

Each DISPLAY statement in GAMS is replaced with a procedure which contains a PUT statement controlled with a suitable *looping* rule ([14], pp. 276). The looping rule is stated in terms of the “driving” index expression (the first argument) and the terms that need to be displayed (second argument). While we have not fully automated this procedure, the following schema can be used to construct the procedure:

```
FILE <ALIAS-NAME> /"operating system path\  
<GAMS-NAME>.TXT/"  
PUT <ALIAS-NAME>;  
<ALIAS-NAME>.PC = 5;  
LOOP(<index expression>,  
    PUT <Out1>...<Outn> /;);
```

- Step 2: Creating database relations.

A relation must be created for each such output, and the data can be imported using database scripts having the following structure:

```
importASCIIvar("<GAMS-NAME>.TXT",  
    "<GAMS-NAME>"," ", TRUE, TRUE);
```

5 Conclusion

The importance of better data modeling and management in mathematical environments has been recognized previously by many researchers. Data management consumes a substantial portion of the effort spent in the design and use of large-scale mathematical modeling systems (see e.g., [15]). The basic dilemma faced by designers and users of decision support systems is the following: mathematical modeling systems are generally weak on data management; database systems do not support representation or manipulation of complex mathematical models. How does one combine the strengths of the two kinds of systems?

In this paper, we have presented an approach for developing decision support systems by integrating model components represented in database and mathematical modeling systems. This approach allows

users to perform each task, such as model development or data management, in the system that is most suitable for the task. While the specific implementation of our approach was in terms of GAMS and Paradox, the ideas are generalizable to other EMLs and relational databases respectively. However, there are several features that we have not implemented as part of our approach.

First, certain mathematical models use *ordered* sets as part of their indexing expressions. GAMS, for example, offers features for ordering sets and for preserving order during set manipulation. We have not investigated how to maintain order when storing and manipulating a set as a database relation. Second, variables in mathematical models may be indexed over any number of index sets. Many of our procedures are implemented and described assuming just two index sets, but is fairly easy to generalize these procedures. Third, the procedures described in §4 require a “metadata” table corresponding to the data definition section of the mathematical model. While this table could automatically be derived by interpreting this section, we have not developed procedures to do so. Fourth, mathematical models can contain fairly complex indexing expressions, and these expressions may have implications on the storage of index set data. Geoffrion [16] presents a taxonomy of indexing structures containing both sets-theoretic and logical expressions. We have not investigated how such structures should influence the database design and storage of data.

Several other researchers have proposed ideas to address the basic dilemma stated above. Fourer [15] investigates the database requirements in mathematical modeling, and presents fundamental principles for developing the database structures required to support a mathematical model. He presents a series of rules for deriving a database model (relational or hierarchical), given a mathematical model formulation—these rules, derived independently from ours, are very similar to our rules presented in §4.2 and illustrated in §2.2.

Fourer also discusses and compares a variety of other approaches for addressing these questions. These may be classified as being integration-oriented (e.g., our approach), data-centric, and model-centric. The data-centric approach relies on the familiarity that people have with database systems. The idea is to extend the mathematical modeling capabilities of database systems. Examples of this approach include Chooibneh’s work on SQLMP extends SQL for mathematical programming [17], as well as in commercial products such as ORACLE (increases features for mathematical analysis) and Microsoft’s OLAP (online analytical processing). This approach also underlies ef-

forts to build spreadsheet based modeling systems such as What's Best! [18] and QuickQuant [19]. However, when compared with EMLs, these tools are not as suitable for developing, understanding, verifying, and maintaining complex mathematical models.

The model-centric approach involves extending the data management features of mathematical modeling systems. While almost all mathematical modeling systems have some features for database management, these features do not have the power of standard desktop database systems. However, two commercial modeling systems, MPL [20] and MIMI/LP [21], do offer significant capabilities for accessing data from a database.

Finally, Geoffrion's *structured modeling* framework [6] and language (SML [4, 5]) allows both the data model and the mathematical model to be described in the same language. In structured modeling systems, a relational model may automatically be derived that stores detailed data for a structured model. This is a promising approach, since many of the database design problems that motivated this paper may entirely be avoided through the use of a structured modeling language. Yet, while many technical approaches now exist for reducing these problems, real progress may come about only through improved modeling practice. In conclusion, as model solution becomes less of an issue in modeling projects, we should expect modelers to place more emphasis on issues such as data management. We hope that this paper is a useful step in the essential direction of improved data management in the mathematical modeling process.

A USMC Trainee Model Data Definition (GAMS)

SETS

I items of syllabus
 P student pilots
 Q instructor pilots

PARAMETERS

HBAR(Q) max flt hrs per day for Q
 H(I) time allowed for each I
 IBAR(P) max training items per day for P
 DHAT(P) days pilot P assigned for training
 NC(P) finished items since assignment of P

TABLE

QUAL(I,Q) qualification of Q to teach item I

PROG(I,P) completed items I for pilot P

ALIAS(I,J)

TABLE

PREREQ(I,J) item I is prerequisite for item J

SCALAR

NTOTAL number of syllabus items in the course
 DTOTAL number of days allowed for training
 CPRIME weight for penalty variable Z
 FTHR flight hour goal on a day T

B Relational Database for Trainee Model

Relation I (event)

I (Key)
 H

Relation Q (Instructor)

Q (Key)
 HBAR

Relation P (Student)

P (Key)
 IBAR
 DHAT
 NC

Relation QUAL (Qualification)

I (Foreign key, primary key for I)
 Q (Foreign key, primary key for Q)
 QUAL

Relation PROG (Progress)

I (Foreign key, primary key for I)
 P (Foreign key, primary key for P)
 PROG

Relation PREREQ (An event that is a prerequisite for another event)

I (Foreign key, primary key for I)
 J (Key)
 PREREQ

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